

MANIFESTATION OF THE EXISTENCE OF TECHNOLOGY IN THE SCIENCE OF PHILOSOPHY

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Abstract. The part of philosophy that studies the issues of existence is called ontology. The word ontology is a combination of the Greek words ontos (existence) and logos (teaching) and means "the doctrine of existence", that is, the science of existence. The part of philosophy that explains the doctrine of existence is called ontology. (This concept was first used in philosophy by H. Wolff).

Key words: existence, ontology, space, time, presence, movement.

The part of philosophy that studies the issues of existence is called ontology. The word ontology is a combination of the Greek words ontos (existence) and logos (teaching) and means "the doctrine of existence", that is, the science of existence. The part of philosophy that explains the doctrine of existence is called ontology. (This concept was first used in philosophy by H. Wolff). This branch of philosophy studies the issues of the universe and existence. The opposite concept of existence is non-existence. Absence means nothing. Nothingness is the beginning and the end of everything, which turns everything into nothing. Therefore, both the creator and the object of existence are non-existence. Existence is existence from non-existence to non-existence. There is no answer to the question of what is absence in science.

What is existence itself? To answer this question, it is necessary to look at the roots of existence related to man and the life of people. Since ancient times, people have been thinking about the surrounding nature and society, people and mankind, and have observed the things and events happening around them, and the changes. Some things exist now and will disappear later, and some things that did not exist yesterday will appear today. On the basis of these, the existence and non-existence

of people, and on this basis, imaginations and views about the world have arisen. The problem of existence has always been considered one of the most controversial parts of philosophy. There are various views on existence, among which religious teachings occupy an important place. In particular, in the Islamic religion, it is understood that "existence is an existence created by God." If we turn to philosophy and literature, we can see that existence is interpreted differently in them. Existence is a philosophical concept that refers to the objective world that exists independently of a person and his mind. Being is eternal, but everything in it is changing and evolving; in the transition from one state to another, from one type to another, because they do not exist from existence, and cannot exist from nothing. Being in the broadest sense, as the most general concept, includes the whole world and all the things and events in it, all the objective and subjective conditions of human life, consciousness, human activity, and even all the processes that take place in society. Therefore, technology, which is a product of the development of society, is also an entity.

The main forms of existence are the following: Nature existence - existence of things (bodies), processes, situations in nature. Human existence - (man's existence in the world of things and his unique human existence). Spiritual being - (individualized and objectified spiritual being). Social existence - (the existence of an individual in the historical process and the existence of society), it is also called social existence. The material form of existence - matter includes all bodies, events, processes and their properties. The direction of the search for commonality specific to the material form of existence is to search for the general essence underlying the material world, to determine the substance. The second way is the search for the "building elements" - the substrate, which is the main part of the material world. The third way is to find the main cause of everything, i.e. pramateria.

Movement. Among the attributes of existence, the characteristic that expresses its main mode of existence is motion. Because the being cannot maintain its structural integrity without movement. There are mechanical, chemical, biological,

physical types of movement, and they are also called changes. Spatial shifts that are common to changes can be manifested in one form or another in all forms of movement. There is such a form of change, which is called development in philosophy. Development is a comprehensive, complex, irreversible, forward-looking, quantitative and qualitative change of a specific system in a specific time and space.

The basic living forms of existence include space and time. If space represents the scope, size, arrangement of things, continuity or continuity, time represents the sequence of events, the duration of processes. Any material body has a place, a scale, a volume. Space reflects the arrangement of points that make up the universe at a particular moment in time, while time represents the sequence of events occurring at a particular point in space. Social movement is the most complex of the forms of movement known to us, in which the conscious activity of a person, human thinking, social thought on the scale of society come together. It is also very difficult to predict its future.

It would not be wrong to say that by studying the category of existence, we began to get acquainted with the true essence of philosophy. After all, it is illogical to deal with other areas of philosophy without solving the problem of existence. Including the study of the existence of technology is the demand of the times.

When analyzing existing problems on the basis of different concepts of technology, the following relationships can be distinguished that form the structure that determines the methods of considering technology: technology and existence, technology and man, technology and socio-cultural world, technology and nature. Accordingly, all philosophical concepts of technology can be formed on the basis of one or another type of relationship, which is considered the most basic. Therefore, one can talk about the ontology of technology, the anthropology of technology, the nature of technology, and the cultural studies of technology. There are such types of philosophical concepts of technology, which, of course, determine the essence of technology and its development prospects in different ways. In this regard, in the

philosophy of technology, there are currently five main approaches to defining technology and its essence: ontological, anthropological, instrumental, evolutionary and religious.

M. Heidegger was the first to scientifically base the ontology of technology and, emphasizing the ontological nature of technology, declares that the main principle of technology as an object is the way of self-realization of humanity. In modern society, technology is of primary importance. Technology not only builds a universal technical world, but also subjugates almost the entire space of existence to its command. Its unique logic permeates the social and human dimensions of history. His instrumental mind amazes the mind of the age. The consequences of tech dominance are varied and long-lasting. Its consequences are difficult to predict. Technical predestination is nearly impossible because it involves predestination of thought, behavior, and consciousness. Technology is not just a means to achieve a specific goal, a means to perform pragmatic tasks. It is manifested as a universal human value on a universal scale. According to him, technology can only be compared with reality. The technique is the most important way to discover the deep features of existence, and it belongs to the field where truth is revealed. Technology allows us to reveal the secrets hidden in nature and society. Presents knowledge about them in real, intact form. At least it allows you to guess. Through the essence of technology, man speaks with existence, hears its call. The decisive essence of the technique lies not in operations and manipulations in general, not even in the use of tools, but in the disclosure of new knowledge. Such disclosure shall be made as a production. In other words, technology is production.

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